

PREPARATION AND STUDY OF HYDROXYTRIAZINES AS ANALYTICAL REAGENTS. PART II. 3-HYDROXY-1-*p*-TOLYL-3-PHENYLTRIAZINE AS A REAGENT FOR PALLADIUM AND COPPER

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Out of five hydroxytriazines studied as analytical reagents, 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-phenyltriazine is found to be a highly selective reagent for the gravimetric estimation of copper and palladium and their separation from a large number of elements by direct weighing. The pH range for quantitative precipitation is from 2.0 to 7.0 and 1.6 to 7.0 respectively with only a slight excess of the reagent. pH between 2.0 and 3.0 is found to be the most suitable as it facilitates the hydrolysis of excess of the reagent and increases specificity. The complexes are stable towards heat and acid and are very granular.

In Part I of this series (Sogani and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 563) a general method of preparing hydroxytriazines and their precipitating characteristics were reported. The present communication describes the study of analytical usefulness of five more compounds. Out of these, 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-phenyltriazine has been examined in detail. It offers an advantage that excess of the reagent can be removed easily by heating the weakly acidic reaction medium whereby it is completely hydrolysed into water-soluble products.

Below pH 3.0 it forms complexes only with Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , V^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , vanadate and molybdate. The complexes given by Cu^{2+} and Pd^{2+} are not decomposed on heating in acidic medium, thus making it a highly specific reagent for the gravimetric determination of these elements by direct weighing and their separation from Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , As^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Ce^{4+} , Th^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , tungstate, phosphate, fluoride, alkali and alkaline earth metals and by use of proper masking agents from Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Sn^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , and molybdate. The composition of the complexes correspond to $(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_3)_2\text{M}$, where M=copper or palladium, and can be represented as shown in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounds were prepared by the method described in the earlier communication (*loc. cit.*). Table I summarises the physical properties of these compounds.

Slightly modified method was used for the preparation of 3-hydroxy-1-*o*-carboxyphenyl-3-phenyltriazine. The compound after precipitation was immediately filtered under suction. It was dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol and filtered. It was reprecipitated by adding a small amount of water. It was again dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol and kept in a refrigerator overnight when white needle shaped crystals separated.

TABLE I

Compound.	Cryst. from	M. P.	Cryst. shape.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-N}(\text{OH})\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{R}$ where R =					
I. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$ (<i>p</i>)	95% Ethanol	*130°	Greenish yellow needles	18.81	18.50
II. $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br}$ (<i>p</i>)	Do	†154°	Deep green shining needles	14.08	14.38
III. $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COOH}$ (<i>o</i>)	Very small vol. of alc.	35°	White needles	16.47	16.15
IV. $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CO.CH}_3$ (<i>p</i>)	95% Ethanol	154°	Light green flakes	16.23	16.47
V. $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH.CO.CH}_3$ (<i>p</i>)	Do	146.5°	Do	20.58	20.74

Lit. M.P. 130° (Bamberger and Busdorf, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 3510), and 131° (Elkins and Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1346).
† Lit. M.P. 154.5° (Bamberger, *Annalen*, 1918, 420, 164).

The general precipitating properties, and colour and nature of complexes formed by these compounds resemble essentially the parent compound (*loc. cit.*). Precipitates formed by *o*-carboxy derivative (III) are gelatinous in nature, unstable towards heat, and unsuitable for analytical purposes. Complexes given by *para*-bromo (II) and tolyl (I) derivatives are more stable towards heat and acid than the parent compound.

Hydrolysability of the Compounds.—Hydroxytriazines hydrolyse on heating in weakly acidic medium, but only some of them hydrolyse to yield water-soluble products. This is an important property which imparts a compound all the advantages of a water-soluble reagent. Any excess of the reagent present in the reaction medium on heating during the normal processing of the complex, if it hydrolyses into water-soluble products, can easily be eliminated by simple washing. The absence of hydrolysed products in the wash water can readily be ascertained by testing with a drop of dilute NaOH solution.

Experiments were conducted to study the hydrolysis of these compounds. Distilled water (150 c.c.), 10% HCl (v/v., 2 c.c.) and 1% ethanolic solution of the compound were taken in a r.b. flask fitted with an air condenser. It was kept on a boiling water bath for about 45 minutes and was occasionally shaken. Complete disappearance of solid matter from the medium indicated complete hydrolysis of the compound into water-soluble products. It was further verified by taking out a drop of the liquid from the flask and testing it with dilute NaOH solution on a spot plate. Unhydrolysed hydroxytriazine shows an intense yellow colour, hydrolysed products give bluish black colour, and incomplete hydrolysis is indicated by a greenish yellow or greenish blue colour, depending on the extent of reaction. The mechanism of hydrolysis has already been reported earlier (*loc. cit.*).

A standard solution was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride (1 g.) in HCl (conc., 5 c.c.) and the solution diluted to one litre. Its palladium content was determined by using dimethylglyoxime. $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.8380 g.) (A. R.) was dissolved in distilled water and made to one litre. The amount of copper in the solution was determined by standard methods. In special cases where sulphate ion interfered, copper acetate was used. 1% Solutions (w/v) of reagent grade soluble salts of various metals were used for quantitative separations.

Normal hydrochloric acid, sodium acetate (10%, w/v), and 10% sodium potassium tartrate solutions were used for adjustment of pH.

A Beckman pH meter, Model H-2, was used for pH measurements, Mettler's single pan balance for weighing, and sintered crucible No. 3 for collecting the precipitates. Ashless filter paper No. 40 was employed for general filtration.

Properties of Complexes.—The palladium complex is yellowish brown in colour, readily soluble in chloroform and benzene, and fairly soluble in ether and acetone. It is only slightly soluble in ethanol. It was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 258° . It is stable towards heat and moderate concentrations of acids and can be safely heated from 120° to 130° to a constant weight in about half an hour. [Found (micro): N, 7.60. $(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_3)_2\text{Pd}$ requires N, 7.51%].

The copper complex is chocolate-brown in colour. As regards stability towards heat and acid and solubility in organic solvents, it resembles palladium complex. It was crystallised from acetone, m.p. $195\text{--}96^\circ$; lit. 191° (Elkins and Hunter, *loc. cit.*). [Found: N, 8.34. $(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O})_2\text{Cu}$ requires N, 8.14%].

Conditions for Quantitative Precipitation.—Various determinations were done using varying amounts of the reagent under different pH conditions. It was found that palladium and copper were

completely precipitated between pH 1.6 and 7.0, and pH 2.0 and 7.0 respectively with only 15 to 20% excess of the reagent. We have, however, carried out the estimations between pH 2.0 and 3.0 as it increased the specificity of the reagent and facilitated removal of the excess reagent by hydrolysis. The precipitates formed under these conditions are very granular.

Procedure for Palladium

A solution of palladium containing 10 to 20 mg. of the metal is diluted to about 120 c.c. 10% Sodium acetate or sodium potassium tartrate (w/v, 2-3 c.c.) and *N*-HCl (2 c.c.) are added to it so as to bring pH of the solution at 2.0-3.0. It is warmed and 1% ethanolic solution of the reagent (about 20% excess) is added with constant stirring. Palladium complex separates as a dirty green precipitate. It is heated on a boiling water bath for about an hour, during which period the precipitate changes its colour to yellowish brown and becomes granular. The supernatant liquid also becomes clear. It is filtered hot through a weighed sintered glass crucible No. 3, washed with hot water 3 to 4 times till the washings do not give bluish violet colour with a drop of NaOH solution. The complex is dried to a constant weight at 120-30°. It takes about half an hour. The weight of the complex multiplied by the conversion factor, 0.1909, gives the weight of palladium. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Pd taken.	Foreign ion.	Pd complex.	Pd found.	Error.	Pd taken.	Foreign ion.	Pd complex.	Pd found.	Error.
20.64 mg.	..	0.1084 g.	20.69 mg.	+0.05 mg.	13.76	Ti ⁴⁺ ,	0.05 0.0723	13.80	+0.04 mg.
13.76	..	0.0720	13.74	-0.02	13.76	Bi ³⁺ ,	0.05 0.0722	13.78	+0.02
6.88	..	0.0362	6.91	+0.03	13.76	Sb ³⁺ ,	0.05 0.0723	13.80	+0.04
20.64	Co ²⁺ , 0.05 g.	0.1083	20.67	+0.03	13.76	Pt ⁴⁺ ,	0.05 0.0720	13.74	-0.02
20.64	Ni ²⁺ , 0.05	0.1082	20.65	+0.01	20.64	Sn ⁴⁺ ,	0.05 0.1084	20.69	+0.05
20.64	Mn ²⁺ , 0.05	0.1084	20.69	+0.05	20.64	Ce ⁴⁺ ,	0.05 0.1082	20.65	+0.01
20.64	Zn ²⁺ , 0.05	0.1080	20.64	0.00	20.64	Zr ⁴⁺ ,	0.05 0.1083	20.67	+0.03
20.64	Cd ²⁺ , 0.05	0.1081	20.63	-0.01	20.64	MoO ₄ ²⁻ ,	0.05 0.1081	20.63	-0.01
13.76	Fe ²⁺ , 0.05	0.0718	13.70	-0.06	20.64	PO ₄ ³⁻ ,	0.10 0.1082	20.65	+0.01
13.76	Fe ³⁺ , 0.05	0.0722	13.78	+0.02	20.64	F ⁻ ,	0.10 0.1084	20.69	+0.05

The interference due to Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Ti⁴⁺, and molybdate was eliminated by adding 0.5 g. of sodium fluoride as a masking agent. The hydrolysis of Sn⁴⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ was also prevented as given above, and that of Ce⁴⁺ by adding a small amount of solid ammonium sulphate. In case of Bi³⁺ and Sb³⁺ sodium potassium tartrate was used as a buffering agent.

Procedure for Copper

The procedure adopted for determining copper is the same as given above. The weight of copper complex multiplied by 0.1232 gives the weight of copper. Table III records the results obtained.

The properties and stabilities of palladium and copper complexes are very similar. Hence observations recorded in case of palladium in presence of foreign ions are also applicable in the case of copper. For the sake of brevity all these have not been included here.

TABLE III
Cu taken = 11.71 mg.

Foreign ion.	Cu complex.	Cu found.	Error.	Foreign ion.	Cu complex.	Cu found.	Error.		
..	0.0949 g.	11.69 mg.	-0.02 mg.	Cd ²⁺ ,	0.05	0.0949	11.69	-0.02	
Co ²⁺ ,	0.05 g.	0.0953	11.74	+0.03	Fe ²⁺ ,	0.05	0.0953	11.74	-0.03
Ni ²⁺ ,	0.05	0.0950	11.70	-0.01	Fe ³⁺ ,	0.05	0.0955	11.76	0.05
Zn ²⁺ ,	0.05	0.0947	11.66	-0.05	Cr ³⁺ ,	0.05	0.0947	11.66	-0.05
Mn ²⁺ ,	0.05	0.0952	11.72	+0.01	Al ³⁺ ,	0.05	0.0955	11.76	-0.05

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-tolyl-3-phenyltriazine is a better reagent than the parent compound in that the reagent as well as the complexes given by it are more stable and the conversion factors more favourable.

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